

RLSTAP Algorithm Development Tool for Analysis of Advanced Signal Processing Techniques

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Abstract

Space Time Adaptive Processing (STAP) has been identified as a key enabling technology for the detection of small targets in the presence of severe clutter and jamming. It is therefore important to develop simulation and analysis tools which accurately model advanced STAP architectures in realistic operational environments and to evaluate evolving system technologies prior to large development programs. This paper describes a user-friendly simulation capability, developed under the ARPA Mountaintop program, which can be used to assess the performance of evolving adaptive processing technologies for advanced airborne surveillance systems.

1. Introduction

The Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA) Mountaintop Program is conducting emulated-motion radar measurements from elevated ground-based locations to provide a database for the study of advanced surveillance and tracking issues. Measurements have been conducted from mountaintop sites including the White Sands Missile Range (WSMR) in New Mexico and the Pacific Missile Range Facility (PMRF) on Kauai, Hawaii using the Radar Surveillance Technology Experimental Radar (RSTER) in conjunction with an Inverse Displaced Phase Center Array (IDPCA) auxiliary antenna [1] for emulation of the airborne environment.

In support of the ARPA Mountaintop Program, the Air Force Rome Laboratory has developed a state-of-the-art tool for analysis of Mountaintop data and evaluation of systems technologies needed to address future operational requirements. The Rome Laboratory Space Time Adaptive Processing Algorithm Development Tool (RLSTAP/ADT) was developed under the Khoros Software Development Environment [2] for user-friendly operation and is designed to support a wide variety of user experiments. Using a

three-button mouse, the user can navigate through the RLSTAP/ADT windows and pull-down menus to process and evaluate measured radar data, simulate ground-based or airborne multi-channel radar data in jamming and clutter environments, combine measured and simulated data, develop and evaluate new STAP algorithms, and assess system performance of advanced signal processing technologies.

2. Recorded Data

The Recorded Data functional group of the RLSTAP/ADT provides the user with easy access to recorded data from actual radar experiments and converts the data file into the Khoros Visualization Image File Format (VIFF) for use in the RLSTAP/ADT. A VIFF header file, which contains information on the radar parameters and the conditions under which the data was collected, is also created for use in the RLSTAP/ADT. Currently, the modules that support processing of Mountaintop data have been implemented and support of additional data formats is planned.

3. Physical Model

The Physical Model functional group of the RLSTAP/ADT contains modules that allow the user to simulate the radar's operational environment from the point of transmission of a selected waveform to the arrival of the return waveform at the receiver. The modules in this section provide the capability to realistically simulate stationary and airborne radar systems, targets, atmospheric conditions, jammers, and clutter environments. Figure 1 illustrates a typical physical model line-up which was created by connecting several functional modules, referred to as *glyphs*, to simulate radar data for targets in the presence of clutter and jamming. The line-up includes an ensemble of modules which define parameters of the

transmit platform, transmit antenna, transmit waveform, targets, jammers, clutter environment, receive antenna platform, and receive antenna, all summed at the input to the receiver. Also shown is a pull-down window for a target which allows the user to select target parameters such as position, heading, velocity, radar cross section, and Swerling characteristics.

Figure 1. Physical model line-up

3.1 Radar system modeling

The Physical Model allows the user to define the parameters of the radar system from the transmitter to the receive antenna and also define the position, orientation, heading, and velocity of the radar platform within the map environment. The transmit waveform function allows the user to define waveform parameters such as pulse width, pulse modulation, number of pulses in a Coherent Processing Interval (CPI), and peak power. The transmit and receive antennas, which are defined separately, are currently assumed to be planar arrays with uniformly spaced elements. User selectable antenna parameters include the number of channels, antenna gain, antenna sidelobe level, and mechanical boresight. Antenna patterns can be defined by selecting element patterns and applying selected weights in azimuth and elevation. The user can also define the position of the transmit and receive antennas on their respective platforms.

3.2 Target modeling

Targets are modeled as point sources with user specifiable RCS. Target fluctuation statistics are defined by Swerling models 0-4. Target position is specified in range, angle, and either height above mean sea level or above ground level using terrain elevation information derived from USGS data. Target heading and velocity are also user specified.

3.3 Jammer modeling

The RLSTAP/ADT includes the ability to model barrage noise, constant-frequency tone, and swept frequency jammers. The barrage noise jammer provides a noise-like voltage sequence over all range gates, pulses, and channels. The tone jammer generates a narrowband complex sinusoid signal over the range of samples. The swept frequency jammer generates an up-chirp LFM complex voltage over range. Jammer locations and orientations are specified in a manner similar to that of targets. Additionally, jammer parameters such as radiated power, modulation type, center frequency, bandwidth, period, duty factor and sweep rate can be selected as default values or specified by the user. Either ground-based or airborne jammers can be modeled.

3.3 Clutter modeling

The RLSTAP/ADT provides a flexible clutter modeling capability which allows users to define the clutter environment to a level that suits their needs. For first order analysis or statistical studies, homogeneous clutter environments can be modeled. For detailed studies or operational analysis, more realistic clutter returns can be generated for a user-specified location using terrain height and terrain cover information available in the United States Geological Survey (USGS) database. This key feature of the RLSTAP/ADT provides a valuable tool for experiment planning or system analysis in environments where data may not exist.

The homogeneous clutter model applies a single user-specified clutter type across the surveillance volume. The site-specific clutter model simulates the clutter environment for a specified location using terrain elevation and terrain cover information available in the USGS database to derive the line-of-sight visibility, grazing angle, and clutter type for each range-angle cell in the surveillance volume. Spatial and temporal clutter statistics are applied to each clutter cell based on the clutter type selected or as defined by the user. The clutter simulation treats each range-angle cell as an individual point scatterer whose signal strength at the receiver is a function of the backscatter coefficient, range, atmospheric attenuation, antenna gain, and system gains/losses. The clutter strength is calculated using the standard radar range equation for clutter and is stored as a complex voltage.

A clutter intensity map generated for the RSTER radar, located on North Oscura Peak (NOP) at WSMR with the antenna pointing in a direction of 280 degrees, is shown in Figure 2. This plot shows the magnitude of the clutter returns in the mainbeam and sidelobes after accounting for the two-way directional antenna gain and the range to each clutter cell.

Figure 2. Clutter Intensity Map

4. Receiver

The Receiver functional group is the means by which various voltage time sequences from the Recorded Data and/or Physical Model are combined. Currently, the receiver is modeled to a level that allows the user to define fundamental receiver parameters and characteristics such as gains/losses, RMS gain variations, system noise figure, and system noise temperature. More detailed modeling of the receiver is planned and will include I/Q channel mismatch, channel-to-channel mismatch, saturation effects, quantization errors, and phase noise effects.

5. Radar signal processing

The Signal Processing functional group provides a library of radar signal processing functions which are commonly used in conventional processing and STAP applications. The modules in this group provide the tools to model radar signal processing techniques which can operate on either physical model data or recorded data. Included in this group are functions such as pulse compression (PC), motion compensation (MotionComp), moving target indication (MTI), Doppler subbanding (DopplerSubb), beamforming (BeamForm), steering vector (SteerVector), STAP rules (STAPRule), covariance matrix (Covar), diagonal loading (DiagLoad), inverse covariance matrix (InvCovar), and adaptive weights (STAPWgts). The modules in this section are designed to allow the user the flexibility to configure processing functions in any order to develop and test signal processing techniques.

5.1 Signal processing algorithms

Most common conventional processing and STAP algorithms can be easily modeled within the RLSTAP/ADT using combinations of the functions listed above to create a user defined signal processing line-up. With the distribution of the RLSTAP/ADT a collection of pre-configured line-ups, or *procedures*, are included which model conventional processing and popular STAP algorithms for researchers to use and/or modify. These algorithms include conventional beamforming (after MTI and Doppler subbanding), Factored Time Space (FTS), Factored Space Time (FST), Joint Domain Optimum (JDO), and Adaptive Displaced Phase Center Array (ADPCA). Discussion of these basic STAP approaches can be found in reports by Jaffer, et al. [3], and Ward [4].

5.2 Algorithm line-up example

There are a few aspects which distinguish one algorithm from another, such as the method of selecting secondary data to form the covariance matrix, the form of the steering vector, and the calculation of the weight vector(s). In the RLSTAP/ADT, these differences in algorithm structure can be seen in the order and selection of modules in the functional flow line-up. As an example, consider the FTS line-up shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. FTS algorithm line-up.

It is typical in most algorithms to pre-process or condition the raw radar range/pulse/element (RPE) data cube. This pre-conditioning may consist of PC, MotionComp and MTI filtering, as seen in the flow of the FTS example. The PC module allows the users to select either an externally generated or internally generated matched filter in either time or frequency. For the internally generated matched filter the user can choose from the following modulation schemes: LFM, CW Barker, LPM, and Polyphase. A predefined matched filter is included in the RLSTAP/ADT for processing recorded RSTER data.

Beyond pre-processing functions the FTS example continues with Doppler subbanding and is followed by adaptive spatial beam forming. The DopplerSubb module allows for time windowing before it performs Doppler filtering using a 1-D Discrete Time Fourier Transform which is applied across the pulse dimension for each channel and at each range.

The FTSSRule module, which comes from the generic STAPRules module, specifies important parameters to the rest of the glyphs *downstream* for the given algorithm. These parameters include adaptive array configuration vs. sidelobe canceler configuration, the range rule parameters to use when estimating the covariance matrix, and which range bins to apply the adaptive weights to.

Once the STAPRules module is defined for a given algorithm, the modules Covar, DiagLoad and InvCovar are executed. A spatial and/or temporal steering vector is formed through the glyph SteerVector and this information is passed to the weight calculation glyph STAPWgts. These two modules, Steer Vector and STAPWgts, get their instructions from the STAPRules as to how to form the required steering vector and weight vector(s) respectively for a given algorithm. The glyph BeamForm applies weight(s) to the previously specified range bins (in STAPRules) of the conditioned input RPE data cube.

The RLSTAP/ADT contains several diagnostic tools for evaluating the performance of signal processing algorithms which can be applied anywhere in the processing chain. Plotting functions include RPE plots, line plots, and a general plot utility which can be used to generate a variety of plots including the adapted antenna pattern, amplitude vs Doppler for a given range, amplitude vs range for a given Doppler filter, range-Doppler, and angle-Doppler.

6. Example scenario

To demonstrate the functionality of the RLSTAP/ADT for simulation and modeling of advanced signal processing technologies, let us consider a notional scenario which includes a "flying RSTER" UHF Airborne Early Warning (AEW) radar system, configured to provide 14 azimuthal degrees of freedom, operating in the strong clutter environment of WSMR and in the presence of a barrage noise jammer, as illustrated in Figure 4. The AEW radar is flying just above the ridge at NOP, similar to the position of the site used for the Mountaintop Program measurements, at a speed of 200 knots and a heading of 250 degrees. The antenna is pointed 30 degrees clockwise from the aircraft's velocity vector. An airborne barrage jammer, which is located 80 km away at an azimuth of 240 degrees and at an altitude of about 2.5 km (8200 feet) above ground level, is radiating in the direction of the AEW radar with an Effective Radiated Power (ERP) of 45 dBW. An aircraft,

with an RCS of 5 dBsm, is located in the mainbeam of the AEW radar antenna at a range of 80 km with a heading of 20 degrees and a velocity of 270 m/s (525 knots). A second airborne target, with an RCS of -20 dBsm, is located at a range of 78 km from the AEW radar with a heading of 45 degrees and a velocity of 1000m/s (1944 knots).

As illustrated in Figure 4, clutter arrives at the antenna from all angles over a wide Doppler extent due to the antenna sidelobes and the motion of the airborne platform. As shown, both targets are separated from the mainbeam clutter due to their respective velocities. The large target can be seen above the sidelobe clutter energy while the small target is obscured by it. Adding a broadband jammer results in raising the interference level to a point where both targets are masked.

Since the jammer energy emanates from a particular direction it can be attenuated by a spatial null enabling detection of the large target. Clutter returns, however, arrive at the receive antenna from all directions and can not be attenuated by purely spatial techniques. Also, temporal techniques such as MTI can not effectively suppress the mainbeam clutter energy due to the Doppler spread caused by aircraft motion. Since the clutter observed by an AEW radar is dependent on both angle and Doppler, algorithms which utilize both spatial and temporal degrees of freedom are necessary to enable detection of the small target in the presence of jamming and clutter. Applying space time processing to cancel the clutter which competes with the Doppler of the target results in the ability to see the small target above the interference.

Figure 4. STAP clutter/jamming suppression

Using the RLSTAP/ADT Physical Model, the described scenario was modeled to generate simulated time-series radar returns for the AEW radar system. The data was then processed using a conventional signal processing technique and the FTS algorithm described above.

The line-up for the conventional processing techniques included PC, three-pulse MTI, MotionComp, DopplerSubb and conventional beamforming. A range-Doppler plot, generated after the beamforming operation, is shown in

Figure 5. Range-Doppler plot after MTI

Figure 5. As can be seen in this plot, conventional processing attenuates much of the mainbeam clutter around zero Doppler, but does not have the necessary degrees of freedom to adequately attenuate the sidelobe clutter and jamming interference that fills in the rest of the Doppler space, resulting in the inability to see either target.

The second method used for processing was the FTS algorithm described in section 5.2. The resulting range-Doppler plot is shown in Figure 6. Note that the FTS algorithm was able to effectively suppress the spatially and temporally dependent interference to a level below that of the targets.

Figure 6. Range-Doppler plot after FTS

6. Conclusion

As illustrated by the results shown in this paper, the current features of the RLSTAP/ADT offer significant capability for processing of measured data, modeling of airborne radar systems, simulation of threat scenarios in adverse operating environments, analysis of STAP algorithms, and development of advanced signal processing architectures. With continued development and feedback from the technical user community, the RLSTAP/ADT will be an increasingly powerful tool for investigating the performance benefits of evolving technologies for advanced airborne surveillance systems.

In support of the ARPA Common Research Environment for STAP Technology (CREST) initiative, Rome Laboratory has installed the RLSTAP tool, along with radar data collected under the Mountaintop Program, at the Maui High Performance Computing Center (MHPCC) on the 400-node IBM POWERParallel SP-2 computer for access by approved researchers via INTERNET. Approved researchers will have the flexibility of downloading the RLSTAP tool, documentation, and Mountaintop data for local processing in addition to utilizing the parallel computing power of the MHPCC.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like thank ARPA Program manager CAPT Eugene Bal (USN) for his continued support of the RLSTAP tool, Technology Service Corporation (TSC) for their support in source code development, and Kaman Sciences Corporation for their support in software integration.

References

- [1.] G.W. Titi, *An Overview of the ARPA Mountaintop Program*, Proceedings of the IEEE Long Island Section Adaptive Antenna Systems Symposium, Melville, NY, 7-8 Nov 94, pp. 53-59.
- [2.] R. Jordan, *Khoros: A Software Development Environment for Data Processing*, DSP Applications, Mar 93, pp. 16-23.
- [3.] A. G. Jaffer, M. H. Baker, W. P. Ballance, J. R. Staub, *Adaptive Space-Time Processing Techniques for Airborne Radars*, Rome Laboratory Technical Report, RL-TR-91-162, Rome, NY, Jul 91
- [4.] J. Ward, *Space Time Adaptive Processing for Airborne Radar*, MIT/LL Report No. 1015, Lexington, MA, Dec 94